

Integrated Research Administration Support

*Broadening Research Administrators' Capacity to
Impact Early-Career Researchers through the
Research Development Knowledgebase*

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A report compiling ideas and input from Research Administration professionals regarding the potential to expand Research Development-related skills, resources, and activities in their repertoire and workflow

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

AUTHORS & ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	4
Funding Acknowledgement	5
Acknowledgement of Participants	5
INTRODUCTION & FINDINGS OVERVIEW	6
Background of Topic	6
Rationale	7
Major Findings	9
CONVENINGS	11
Timeline of Activities	11
Approach to Information Collection & Analysis	12
SUPPORT BY RA STAFF FOR EARLY-CAREER FACULTY RESEARCHERS	14
Faculty Support Requests	14
Investing Time for Faculty Success	16
INTERESTS FROM RA STAFF IN RD ACTIVITIES	18
Incorporating New RD Activities	18
Reasons behind RA Professionals' Activity Choices	20
NEEDS FOR RA STAFF TO MOVE INTO THE RD SPACE	22
Barriers to Implementing RD Activities	22
Facilitators of RD Activities	23
RECOMMENDATIONS FOR GROWING INTEGRATED RESEARCH SUPPORT	25
For Research Administration (RA) Staff and Professional RA Organizations	26
For Research Development (RD) Staff and Professional RD Organizations	27
For Senior Faculty, Administration, and Leadership	28
For Early-Career Faculty	29
CONCLUSION & NEXT STEPS	30
What We're Taking Away	30
Where We (and Others) May Go Next	30
REFERENCES	31
APPENDIX A: GLOSSARY OF KEY TERMS	33
APPENDIX B: PARTICIPANT DEMOGRAPHICS	35
APPENDIX C: RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES	37

AUTHORS & ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors met through a statewide organization called the [Florida Research Development Alliance \(FL-RDA\)](#). Their collective expertise and experience include Research Development (RD) and Research Administration (RA) positions at large (R1) and smaller (non-R1), public and private institutions. This group implemented a grant-funded project to better understand opportunities to grow support for early-career faculty researchers in diverse institutional settings. This report is an output of their investigation of higher education staff and infrastructure.

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With this funding, the project team explored ways that the Research Development (RD) knowledgebase could be utilized by various institutional stakeholders to the benefit of supporting early-career faculty. A particular focus was on individuals without formal RD positions, such as those working in Research Administration (RA), those who mentor early-career faculty (such as senior faculty and administrators), and others charged with creating and growing their institution’s research enterprise.

Acknowledgement of Participants

The authors wish to extend great thanks to the many focus group participants and survey respondents who contributed their experiences, ideas, and feedback for this project.

INTRODUCTION & FINDINGS OVERVIEW

Motivated by a desire to enhance support for early-career faculty in diverse institutional settings, a series of information collection activities were conducted from 2023-2024. These activities included focus groups and surveys with a variety of institutional stakeholders from professional research staff to faculty and administrators. The aim was to explore the current types of support being provided to early-career faculty researchers by various institutional members and consider opportunities to share favored Research Development (RD) activities with those who do not hold formal RD position titles or functions. This report summarizes a subset of the findings from the pool of data gathered during this project, with a particular focus on information collected from Research Administration (RA) staff. *(For the purposes of this report, **Figure 1** defines RD and RA. See **Appendix A** for a Glossary for definitions of RD and RA, along with definitions for other key terms used throughout this report.)*

Research Development (RD)	Research Administration (RA)
Strategic activities to grow an institution's research enterprise, including faculty development, team formation, research promotion, and other capacity building approaches.	Operational and compliance aspects of managing research funding, ensuring adherence to institutional, sponsor, and regulatory requirements.

Figure 1: Defining Key Roles of Research Development (RD) and Research Administration (RA) Professionals

➤ Background of Topic

Research grants provide critical funding for universities, supporting campus infrastructure and faculty research, particularly in STEM fields where grant writing is often essential for promotion and tenure (Boardman & Ponomariov, 2009; Cola & Wang, 2017; U.S. Department of Education, 2023). However, faculty at institutions outside the top research universities face disadvantages in securing substantial grant funding, as federal research dollars are disproportionately awarded to a small group of Carnegie-classified “R1” universities (Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching, 2020; Matthews, 2012). Faculty at non-R1s often work in institutional environments with less research infrastructure, less dedicated time for research, heavier teaching loads, fewer or no RD staff, and a reliance on limited RA staffing for grant seeking support. In terms of RA staff, higher education institutions typically employ these professionals, or others who are responsible for the role of regulatory compliance, needing these staff to help faculty comply with the requirements for federal grants both pre- and post-award (Schiller & LeMire, 2023). In terms of RD staff, these positions are much more limited, with over half of RD professionals employed by R1 institutions,

two-thirds of all known RD positions found within 14 states, and only larger state or private universities employing multiple RD positions (Preuss et al., 2020). Furthermore, when employed at R1 institutions, RD staff are largely concentrated in central offices, with opportunities for staff at the college and department levels to complement central capacity with RD support distributed across the university.

Research-emerging institutional contexts are particularly challenging for early-career faculty who have little formal training or experience in grant writing and face barriers such as resource constraints, competing priorities, and unsupportive policies (Etzkowitz, 1990; Goff-Albritton et al., 2022). Addressing these challenges requires institutions to foster a supportive research culture, provide educational resources, and offer expert administrative assistance. Often these solutions lie in the hands of RA and RD professionals.

Given the human resource limitations at smaller non-R1 institutions and a continued institutional desire to grow in research, research administration has evolved to include additional functions like RD (Preuss et al., 2020; Zink et al., 2022). RD-type support plays an essential role in elevating an institution's research enterprise with its aim to grow research capacity, enhance collaborations, and support proposal development (Eck & Roney, 2023; National Organization of Research Development Professionals, n.d.). Commenting on how the RA workforce is changing, Zink and colleagues note, "Research development is critical to elevate the prestige of the research enterprise, and it is quickly becoming an essential role" (p. 136).

Prior research on faculty research-support needs has mostly come from the faculty perspective or from their senior colleagues and administrators (Goff-Albritton et al., 2022). This project fills a gap in research on early-career faculty support services and needs by providing a professional RA and RD staff perspective, with a particular focus on the RA perspective in the current report.

Rationale

This project serves to highlight the potential for synergy between the fields of RA and RD. There is opportunity to leverage the interests and competencies of RA staff, who are located across the variety of higher education institutions in the U.S., and who may or may not have formal RD positions or responsibilities (Preuss et al., 2020). RA staff can adopt RD-related approaches and activities into their existing workflow to enhance faculty support, increase organizational capacity and impact, and open new avenues for their own professional growth and advancement. As institutions continue to set strategic plans and goals for growth in sponsored research, an ever-improving research ecosystem is necessary to support those ends, with new specializations within RA needed across the research lifecycle (Zink et al., 2022; Goff-Albritton et al., 2022). RD as a field has also seen expansion and specialization in its breadth of support over the past two decades (Eck & Roney, 2023; Eck, 2023). Taken together, these evolutions in professions create

opportunities for high-impact collaboration between the knowledge bases and professionals in the sister fields of RA and RD (Bauer et al., 2025; Roney & Gabrus, 2022; Scarpinato & Viviani, 2023).

Research administrators bring extensive knowledge and expertise, guiding faculty through many critical aspects of sponsored research like institutional policies and sponsor administrative, financial, and compliance requirements. They play key roles in proposal and budget development, and apply project management principles to ensure compliant proposals are submitted successfully. RD activities complement these efforts by fostering faculty connections, enhancing proposal competitiveness, and strategizing grant seeking approaches. With expertise drawing from areas like team science, business, humanities, psychology, and related social science fields, the RD skillset helps strengthen faculty researchers' confidence, abilities, and success in securing external funding. Research administrators can integrate RD strategies to expand their impact, providing comprehensive support that enhances research success and institutional growth.

RA professionals are positioned to be prime users of RD approaches and resources, integrating RD with their RA expertise and other relevant skillsets to the benefit of early-career faculty and institutional advancement (see **Figure 2** below). As part of a larger project, this report shares about the authors' engagement with RA staff to understand the services they are already providing to early-career faculty, their interests in RD activities, and what skills or support they would need to expand their RD repertoire. Recommendations for various higher education stakeholder groups and key takeaways are summarized in the closing.

Figure 2: Framework for Integrating the RD Knowledgebase with RA Support Approaches and Activities

➤ Major Findings

With a focus on RA staff, especially those involved in pre-award activities, this report organizes findings from focus groups and surveys from nearly 300 participants. Its purpose is to elucidate the RA professional’s role and potential in enhancing support for early-career research. Ideas are explored related to leveraging RA expertise and existing workflows, exploring RA staff interests in RD activities, and understanding their needs for leading new RD-focused initiatives. Nearly half of all RA staff participants indicated interest in engaging in new RD activities, supporting the need for more information about and guidance for this professional group in this area. Find in **Figure 3** a summary of key findings from each topic area of this report.

Figure 3: Major Findings of the Current Investigation Organized into Three Content Areas Related to RA Staff and Their Work

The subsequent section on “Convenings” provides an overview of all data collection activities supported by an NSF GRANTED award, with a particular focus in the current report on those data collected from the NCURA and FRAC groups (see **Appendix B** for details on samples). The major findings of the current investigation can be organized into three content sections related to RA staff and their work: (1) supporting early-career researchers, (2) interest in RD activities, and (3) moving into the RD space. The report concludes with recommendations for various stakeholder groups as well as suggested future directions for research and practice.

Special Note: *The data captured in this report was in advance of the significant federal funding landscape changes of 2025, which further adds to the RA administrative burden but significantly underscores the need for implementation of RD-related activities.*

CONVENINGS

Through focus groups and surveys, 461 participants provided ideas and input on the topic of supporting early-career faculty researchers. A subset ($n=299$) of this collected information is summarized in this report.

Participating staff, faculty, and administrators came from a mixture of public and private higher education institutions, including minority-serving, primarily-undergraduate, and emerging-research institutions. They ranged from RA and RD professionals to early-career faculty members along with senior colleagues and leaders who mentor them. They were recruited to participate through listserv emails sent through statewide and national professional organizations, including FL-RDA, NCURA, and FRAC (acronyms explained in the timeline graphic).

See **Appendix B** for full demographic characteristics for all participants in the larger project. **The primary focus of this report is on the RA participants and respondents, namely the NCURA and FRAC samples collected in 2024.**

➤ Timeline of Activities

A total of nine activities engaged participants during the September 2023 through July 2024 time period (see **Figure 4**), and for each stakeholder group often commenced with a focus group often commenced with a focus group “convening” followed by a survey.

Figure 4: Timeline of Data Collection Activities

➤ Approach to Information Collection & Analysis

The authors served as facilitators of focus groups and survey administrators, which led to the collection of data summarized herein. As depicted in the timeline, smaller focus group events were followed by surveys to larger audiences. See **Figure 5** for the key features of each data collection technique used in the current project.

	Focus Groups	Surveys
Size	5-35 participants per event, with subgroups (at larger events) for smaller group discussions	20-200+ responses per survey, scaling with the size of the professional organization surveyed
Format	Some more traditional focus group style with speaking recorded, others used a “guided reflection” booklet to document responses to prompts	Incorporated multiple choice, ranking, Likert-style, and open-ended questions; about 10-15 main questions per survey (with additional demographic items)
Purpose	Test survey questions to ensure they are understood by and appropriate for each audience, allow facilitators to ask follow-up questions in response to participant ideas (not afforded by surveys), facilitate sharing of ideas between participants	Collect information from a larger group on questions that performed well in the focus group setting (or where additional information is desired), modify the nature or content of the focus group questions to dig more deeply into topics of interest

Figure 5: Summary of Data Collection Techniques and Project Data
(for more details on participants see **Appendix B**)

This multi-step method of data collection is akin to an *exploratory sequential mixed methods design* (Creswell, 2014). According to this design, an initial exploratory phase collects qualitative data from a small group of individuals (such as through focus groups) and then is followed up by a more quantitative phase with a larger group (such as through surveys). In between the two phases, the project team analyzes the information collected from the qualitative phase (focus group) to inform question development for the quantitative phase (survey). In keeping with good methodological procedures, both phases collect information from the same population but are not the same samples. Additionally, aiming to maintain credibility and trustworthiness in the analysis, the team completed iterative rounds of coding the collected data, searching for confirming and disconfirming evidence (Patton, 2015; Saldaña, 2021).

As an example of how the two data collection steps were beneficial, take the following case. A focus group prompt revealed many types of support provided to early-career researchers, which were captured through audio recording and transcription of participant responses. Next, these types of support were thematically grouped by the project team. In the follow-up survey, respondents were asked to rate each type of support identified by the focus group, both in terms of how easy it would be to implement the support and the anticipated size of the support’s impact.

Using this approach, the project team did not have to assume the types of support typically provided to early-career faculty, but instead collected that information directly from the population of interest (through the focus group). With the second step, the team delved deeper into the question of feasibility and potential outcomes related to each type of support in an efficient way (through the survey).

The two-step process of focus group followed by a survey was employed with multiple populations (each population is represented by a professional organization’s membership) and provided an additional opportunity to evolve the types of questions being asked over time. For example, RA professionals participated in two rounds of focus groups and two rounds of surveys; data were collected from both the statewide FRAC organization and national NCURA organization. This afforded a chance to follow up on and explore more deeply topics and themes that were emerging as interesting and fruitful.

One way that the topics evolved over time was from a focus on early-career faculty researchers and how professional staff support them, to more of a focus on the professional staff members themselves and their interests, experiences, and workplaces. See examples of questions used to survey the various stakeholder groups in **Figure 6**.

Sample Survey & Focus Group Questions		
RA Staff	RD Staff	Faculty & Mentors
Which of the following research development-oriented activities would you be interested in incorporating into your work?	What do you find is the most valuable support you provide to early-career faculty? Think about both the simple things you do and the more time- and resource-intensive support you give.	<i>(for the Faculty)</i> What help do you still need to better assist in your research endeavors? (Consider what you need for both short- and longer-term success.)
What could support you to incorporate this new RD activity into your work? (Consider how to remove barriers and tap into facilitators of this new activity.)	What data or other strategic information do you provide to early-career faculty to help them make decisions about their research activities?	<i>(for the Mentors)</i> What do early-career faculty most commonly ask for your help with related to supporting their research?

Figure 6: Example Survey and Focus Group Questions for Three Stakeholder Groups

The primary focus of this report is on data collected from RA staff members, but information about questions from all groups that participated in the larger project are also described above, as earlier stages of the project were key to informing later stages.

FINDING

SUPPORT BY RA STAFF FOR EARLY-CAREER FACULTY RESEARCHERS

Early-career faculty researchers who receive support from knowledgeable mentors and support persons can accelerate their awareness, understanding, and skillset related to grant seeking. Ultimately, these learnings can lead to securing extramural grants, providing funding that is essential to launching the research careers of many assistant professors.

As is noted in the introduction, prior research on this topic mostly focuses on faculty needs from their own perspective and from the perspective of those senior faculty and college/department administrators who advise and mentor them. This project fills a gap in the information space related to early-career faculty, complemented by providing a professional staff perspective. With input from RA professionals from both state (FRAC) and national (NCURA) organizations (see **Appendix B** for details on these samples), we captured experiences and recommendations related to supporting members of the early-career faculty group, who are working to establish themselves in the research and funding arenas.

► Faculty Support Requests

In reporting what faculty most commonly ask for their help with, RA staff shared a variety of topics they are consulted on. These topics ranged from the personal, such as faculty requesting advice on how to plan and manage their time, to the more structural, like how to use online portals and follow institutional procedures. ***These are important findings as they demonstrate how early-career faculty view the role of an RA professional, in addition to highlighting the potential for additional knowledge and support that RA staff could provide by integrating RD perspectives.***

RA staff are helpful in getting their new faculty members started with foundational knowledge and guidance on how to begin. Find below a collection of survey responses from RA professionals regarding faculty requests for support in this domain.

“UNDERSTANDING HOW TO APPLY, HOW TO GET SUPPORT WITH APPLICATIONS, WHAT RESOURCES WE HAVE FOR WRITING THAT FIRST GRANT APPLICATION.”

“FINDING FUNDING FOR PROJECTS OR WHAT TYPES OF FUNDING WOULD WORK BEST FOR THEM.”

“UNDERSTANDING INTERNAL PROPOSAL APPROVAL PROCEDURES.”

“PREPARING SUPPLEMENTARY DOCUMENTS, BROADER IMPACTS SECTION, COST SHARE BUDGETING.”

“THEY WANT TEMPLATES OR SAMPLE PROPOSALS.”

These RA professionals were also consulted for their input on project ideas, how to connect with potential collaborators, how to position the problem statement in a proposal, balancing research and teaching responsibilities, and navigating relationships with department chairs and college deans. In terms of providing this more holistic support to faculty, RA respondents had the following to say in terms of what else they provide assistance with:

“ADVICE ON STRATEGIC PLANNING FOR RESEARCH GRANTS AND EDITING PROPOSALS.”

“UNDERSTANDING HOW TO PREPARE A COMPELLING APPLICATION THAT IS NOT A MIRROR OF SOMEONE ELSE’S AWARDED PROJECT, CONVEY ‘THEIR’ STORY.”

“APPROACHING A CHAIR/RESEARCH DEAN WHO IS NOT ENGAGED.”

“GUIDING THEM ON HOW TO REACH OUT TO PROGRAM OFFICERS AND POTENTIAL COLLABORATORS.”

A final quote by one RA staff member was revealing in terms of how they viewed their role in relation to early-career faculty:

“AN [RA STAFF MEMBER] SHOULD MEET WITH FACULTY TO INTRODUCE THEMSELF, TO MINDFULLY GET A BETTER UNDERSTANDING OF THEIR RESEARCH. THROUGH THIS EXCHANGE QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS MAY BEGIN TO SURFACE ABOUT WHAT THE RESEARCHER NEEDS. WHEN THE FACULTY MEMBER REALIZES THEY HAVE ADMINISTRATION ON THEIR SIDE TO HELP FACILITATE, NOT COMPLICATE, THE PROCESS, THE RESEARCHER CAN MAKE CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE SOLUTIONS. THIS HELPS SET THE PRELIMINARY FRAMEWORK FOR BETTER COLLABORATIVE EFFORTS.”

While additional context is not provided for interpreting how they approach their “coach” role, the notion is highly relevant for conceptualizing an integrated form of RA support that incorporates elements of RD such as strengths and needs assessments, grant strategy, career planning and decision making, network development, and other areas for enhanced faculty support.

➤ Investing Time for Faculty Success

RA staff were invited to consider what they would do if provided half a day per week to better support early-career faculty researchers. We thought it was important to create this theoretical space in their schedule so that they would not be overly constrained in their thinking. Practically, responses to this question can help prompt ideas for how to adapt and enhance current forms of support. These adaptations and enhancements may come with some initial and recurring time investment. However, this time investment should not preclude their consideration. Their thoughts are summarized in **Figure 7** and expanded upon in this section. ***As “boots on the ground” support persons, RA staff have special insights into the needs of early-career faculty that are unmet by prior training/experience or others on campus.***

The most common plans mentioned by RA staff related to providing more direct support and training opportunities for early-career faculty. In terms of direct support, one-on-one consultations were mentioned frequently. RA professionals wanted the time and space to provide “proactive support,” walking faculty through the proposal process, as well as to help them find funding opportunities and provide feedback on their proposal documents. These staff were open to scheduling individual meetings or holding office hours or Q&A sessions for faculty to drop in. Some mentioned the value of recurring meetings with faculty, using some for strategy and check-in, but mostly being driven by questions brought by faculty members. One quote from a survey respondent encapsulates the value these one-on-one meetings can provide:

“WE SHOULD ALWAYS APPROACH THEIR UNDERSTANDING AS IF WE ARE THEIR COACH.”

The other most popular response by RA staff was a desire to develop and implement training for faculty. This training was variously referred to as presentations, workshops, webinars, videos, tutorials, brown bags, bootcamps, conferences, onboarding, academies, courses, learning modules, and information/knowledge transfer sessions. A variety of training topics were mentioned, such as interpreting an RFP, grant budgeting, proposal writing, project management,

Reimagining Support: Perspectives and Priorities on Time Well Spent

Direct Support	Training Opportunities
Online and Material Infrastructure Enhancements	Networking Events and Connection Facilitation
Evaluation of Service Effectiveness and Process Improvements	Personal Professional Development and Wellbeing

Figure 7: RA Staff Preferences for Growing Early-Career Faculty Support

effort reporting, and other aspects of basic research administration. RA professionals who plan to develop trainings may do well to follow the suggestion of one survey respondent to start slow and simple, expanding on additional information when it becomes necessary:

“SMALL DOSES OF PROCESS AND PROCEDURES, LIKE A TWO-MINUTE DRILL FOR EACH TOPIC AND THEN EXPOUND ON IT...LIKE UNWRAPPING AN ONION. START WITH THE GENERAL AND MOVE TO THE SPECIFIC.”

Mentioned somewhat less frequently, though still covered by many respondents, was the need for improving online and material infrastructure for grant seeking. RA staff were interested in creating and disseminating grant-related support forms, “how-to” guides, “to-do” lists, checklists, timelines, guidance materials, job aids, templates, tools, databases, toolkits, handbooks, manuals, information packets, and a library of resources. In this area, updating one’s office or institutional website and developing online resources was also mentioned as needed.

RA staff recognized the interest by new faculty in connecting with others around campus. These connections serve the purpose of cultivating intra-institutional collaborations and learning from more experienced researchers. RA professionals felt that by learning more about faculty research interests, they could better identify and recommend potential professional connections. Organizing “synergy meetings,” luncheons, and other types of networking events were suggested as possible solutions. Creation of a formal mentoring program that matches early-career and experienced faculty was also mentioned.

Some RA professionals wanted to assess how effective their support services were in order to enact process and policy improvements. Others were interested in developing themselves professionally, such as through attending seminars and reading published articles relevant to their work. Several RA staff members mentioned the value of caring for their own wellbeing as important, including time to rest and recharge.

FINDING

INTERESTS FROM RA STAFF IN RD ACTIVITIES

The RA skillset can be reinforced and enhanced by inclusion of RD-oriented knowledge and competencies. With a strong foundation in regulations, compliance, budget development, and administrative standard processes, the pre-award RA professional's work can be further strengthened in serving faculty needs with an RD approach and set of resources. The RD approach is one that is focused on strategy, the “big picture,” idea generation, career development, and offering customized advice to faculty. This is not to say that aspects of RA activities are not RD-like, but that the driving purpose of each professional approach is different yet complementary. This becomes the strength of an **“integrated RA approach,”** using both RA and RD lenses for viewing support opportunities for faculty members. While both can center around a grant proposal, the RD approach pushes the support to go beyond the immediate requirements of a proposal to include broader faculty development needs, the surrounding research environment, and the role the RA staff member can play in nurturing research careers. As mentioned in the introduction, this is particularly important at non-R1 institutions with less or no dedicated RD staff or infrastructure.

By collecting preferences of RA professionals for engaging in various RD activities, we can understand what from the RD knowledgebase is likely to be of interest to and accessed by RA staff. Specifically, this information was collected by engaging RA professionals from both state (FRAC) and national (NCURA) organizations. ***In contrast to the prior section focused specifically on early-career faculty, the current and subsequent sections of this report provide perspectives in relation to faculty overall. Additionally, these remaining findings sections dig deeper into the range of RD-specific activities of interest to RA staff (especially those RA staff engaged in pre-award activities) as well as the rationale for and practicalities of their implementation.***

Incorporating New RD Activities

When asked to choose from potential RD activities to incorporate into their work, RA survey respondents were most interested in 13 of the 22 listed RD activities (see **Figure 8** next page; the full list of activities is provided in **Appendix C** and was generated by accessing professional sites and academic publications related to RD). These top RD activities were of interest to over half of the surveyed sample (this sample included 88 staff members with majority pre-award RA responsibilities).

Most Favored RD Activities by RA Staff	
RD Activity	# of Interested RA Staff (out of 88 total)
Create faculty mentoring programs	59 (67%)
Develop training materials, toolkits, workshops	59 (67%)
Work with chairs/deans to customize support	58 (66%)
Organize program officer visits	56 (64%)
Increase institutional capacity, strategic planning	54 (61%)
Host panel events with senior researchers	53 (60%)
Facilitate team science and team building	51 (58%)
Maintain library of successful proposals	50 (57%)
Coordinate multi-disciplinary interest groups of faculty	49 (56%)
Connect faculty with diversity, education resources	49 (56%)
Meet with faculty to strategize long-term research plans	48 (55%)
Help enable collaborative/strategic partnerships	48 (55%)
Facilitate faculty networking and collaboration	45 (51%)

Figure 8: RA Staff Survey Responses When Asked to Choose from Potential RD Activities to Incorporate into Their Work

Three of the top activities related to interest in organizing various activities, including mentoring programs, program officer visits, and long-term research planning for faculty. RA staff were also very interested in creating and managing material resources available to faculty, such as sample successful proposals, educational materials, and diversity information. Other RA professionals wanted to work with different levels of leadership to assist with research capacity building, strategic planning, and customization of support services. Finally, supporting networking, collaboration, and partnerships was of interest to many RA staff members.

When considering where RA staff are located within their university, whether in a central office or within a college/department setting, the following similarities and differences in RD activity preferences emerged (see **Figure 9** next page). Both groups were very interested in developing training materials, toolkits, and workshops for faculty. There was a greater preference by central office staff to want to work with department chairs and deans to customize support services and create faculty mentoring programs. At the department and college level, RA staff were most interested in maintaining a library of successful proposals and organizing program officer visits.

RD Activity Preferences by Staff Location

For Central Office Staff	For Department/College Staff
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Work with chairs/deans to customize support 2. Create faculty mentoring programs 3. Develop training materials, toolkits, workshops 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maintain library of successful proposals 2. Develop training materials, toolkits, workshops 3. Organize program officer visits

Figure 9: RD Activity Preferences for RA Staff Located in a Central Office or in a Department/College Setting

Of note, every one of the 22 RD activities listed in the survey was at least of moderate interest to a significant portion of survey respondents (respondents also had the option to indicate “not interested” or “already do” in relation to each activity, and these responses were omitted in the current analysis). The two least favored RD activities—“*Find and disseminate funding opportunities*” and “*Editing proposals, providing strategic feedback*”—were each still of interest to over 30% of pre-award RA survey respondents. ***The breadth of interest in traditionally RD-oriented activities by RA staff provides opportunity and importance around ensuring professionals in the RA field have access to best practices and resources that typically circulate in the RD field.***

➤ Reasons behind RA Professionals’ Activity Choices

RA professionals provided several reasons for their choice when picking a new RD-type activity they would like to try incorporating into their work. These reasons fall into three themes: (1) making work meaningful and helpful, (2) desire for collaboration and connection, and (3) learning and personal development (see **Figure 10**).

When thinking about the value RA professionals could provide through RD activities to faculty, leadership, and their institution, many topics were mentioned. RA professionals keep current with federal funding trends and expectations, so they can advise various institutional stakeholders in this area. Additionally, ensuring the thoughtful design of research projects to ensure compliance with regulations can set faculty up for better, more productive research programs.

Outcomes of RA + RD

Figure 10: Benefits Perceived by RA Staff for Moving in the RD Space

Others saw the need for clear, concise, and accessible information related to proposals and compliance, which they were willing to provide. It was identified across many responses that faculty, especially those new to their position, have a great need for enhanced support; one example response from an RA professional is provided speaking to this need:

Several of the RD activities chosen by RA staff were viewed as opportunities to form and strengthen

“NEW FACULTY ARE BASICALLY THROWN INTO A SINK-OR-SWIM SCENARIO WITH VERY LITTLE TO NO TRAINING ON HOW TO NAVIGATE THE BASICS OF THE RESEARCH ADMINISTRATION WORLD.”

connections with individuals around campus, from faculty themselves to various levels of leadership, including department chairs, college deans, and others. They viewed these connections as opportunities to impart information—several respondents noted the need for deliberate outreach and communication efforts—as well as to be part of research-related decision making for their institution.

In terms of their own learning and development, many RA staff expressed their RD activity choice as an opportunity to move into an area they have limited experience in. They were excited by the potential challenges and opportunities moving into the new RD space would afford. Importantly, many factors were listed that may hinder and support RD activity as a new role. These barriers and facilitators are described in the next section.

FINDING

NEEDS FOR RA STAFF TO MOVE INTO THE RD SPACE

To enable support that integrates RD with RA, a consideration regarding the barriers and facilitators related to embarking on this integration of work needs to be examined. By engaging with RA staff (data collected from the NCURA and FRAC groups; see **Appendix B** for sample details), including those who serve as directors of sponsored program units, issues related to heavy work burdens and prioritizing tasks surfaced. In considering how to leverage various types of support for integrating RD activities, participants had many ideas ranging from stakeholder support, effective tools and systems, and professional development opportunities. Specific barriers and facilitators are reviewed next (a summary of these are presented in **Figure 11**).

➤ Barriers to Implementing RD Activities

Several major themes emerged around the topic of potential barriers for the RA staff member related to implementing new RD activities. Issues involving widespread challenges being faced by sponsored programs offices, lack of organizational support, and other concerns were expressed.

In contrast to a desire to be more *proactive* in their support of faculty, RA professionals lamented the *reactive* nature of much of their work. Reactive work came in the form of attending to last-minute proposal submissions, filling in during staff turnover, dealing with inefficient systems and workflows, among other time constraints.

RA staff predicted that a lack of institutional leadership or supervisor support for RD-oriented work would be an obstacle. This could especially be the case for support activities without obvious return on investment or a lack of staff member expertise for providing the support. They were concerned that faculty may not be receptive to receiving this new type of support from their office, leading to a lack of participation in the services or programming offered. Finally, there were concerns that there may not be support from other

Figure 11: Barriers and Facilitators Related to Incorporating New RD Activities into RA Work

units on campus, such as a central RA office disagreeing with the types of activities that should be performed by college-level RA units.

Facilitators of RD Activities

Stepping into new territory (RD or otherwise) requires support—for the individual implementing the new activity and from those surrounding them. RA professionals mentioned various ways that leadership, systems, tools, and other resources could be leveraged to ease the implementation of new RD-focused activities.

Leadership support was seen as an important precursor to new activity in the RD space. Leaders have the capacity to implement and enforce a required internal deadline in advance of the sponsor’s deadline (e.g., “5-day rule”) and make staffing decisions to enable greater time and emphasis on new activities. Leaders could benefit from understanding the value of RD activities and engage in collaborative strategic planning and decision making to inform new grant-related initiatives. While leader input is important, it should be paired with granting a degree of autonomy for the RA staff and office to be responsive and adaptive while the new initiative is being created and implemented. Finally, leaders were seen as needed to help publicize new RD services (lending credibility), hold faculty accountable for grant and research productivity, and give recognition and rewards for accomplishing the new activity. This encouragement would provide motivation for faculty to use the new services and enhance the payoff.

In addition to leadership support, collaboration and input from others on campus were seen as valuable. Examples of this type of support include collecting feedback from constituents on research-related topics and needs, or tapping IT support for development of online resources. Ideas from other participants included crafting guides and resources that efficiently support faculty accountability in their proposal development, freeing up time for RA staff to provide new or enhanced support services. Some thought early-career faculty may be especially inclined to independently access such resources. See the below quote related to one respondent’s idea about this greater faculty autonomy:

“PROVIDING MORE MATERIALS TO FACULTY SO THAT THEY HAVE MORE RESPONSIBILITY IN THE GRANT DEVELOPMENT PROCESS, LEAVING MORE TIME FOR ME TO PROVIDE APPROPRIATE FEEDBACK AND OVERSIGHT TO THEM.”

Beyond support from key stakeholders, the importance of functional tools and systems were emphasized. Efficient organizational processes, access to electronic databases/portals, and effective design and use of other types of grant and research infrastructure that RA staff interface with were brought forward as important facilitators.

To move into a new RD-oriented space, RA staff were interested in engaging in professional development, such as observing others facilitating RD activities, learning from peer institutions and existing program models, attending professional conferences and webinars, and, as one respondent put it:

“DOING MY HOMEWORK ON THIS ACTIVITY.”

This latter comment brings up the question of whether RA staff have easy access to the RD knowledgebase, resources, and professional communities to enable their learning and enhance service development.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR GROWING INTEGRATED RESEARCH SUPPORT

To realize an integrated RA support model, research administrators can become change agents and facilitators, reshaping how their role is perceived and accessed across the institution as well as gathering useful resources and approaches from the RD knowledgebase. Research developers can be resource bearers and collaborators, equipping research administrators with the skills, tools, and other resources needed to enhance faculty support. Senior faculty and institutional leaders must serve as enablers and champions, creating a supportive environment for RA professionals to learn and implement new ways of working. This coordinated approach ultimately benefits both early-career and experienced faculty in a variety of institutions, especially in resource-limited settings, by providing them strategic, proactive support that fosters learning, confidence, and grant success. Specific recommendations for achieving this vision through the work of each stakeholder group are presented below.

Stakeholders Poised to Enact a Progression of Change: Integrating RA and RD Support Approaches for Faculty Success

Figure 12: Stakeholder Engagement to Support Implementation of an “Integrated RA Support” Model

For Research Administration (RA) Staff and Professional RA Organizations

RA staff are key players in the research ecosystem, providing essential administrative, budget, and regulatory compliance support for faculty in their grant seeking. To increase their effectiveness and institutional impact, RA professionals should proactively engage with faculty, develop new tools and resources, and seek opportunities for skill development. By partnering with RD professionals and institutional leadership, RA staff can strengthen their role as strategic contributors to research success. The following recommendations highlight actions RA staff and their professional organizations can take to enhance their effectiveness and professional growth.

1. **Engage Leadership and Faculty** – Build relationships with institutional leaders and faculty to advocate for RA expertise and increase referrals, creating a culture of mutual respect that increases the efficiency and ease in the working relationship.
2. **Develop Targeted Interventions** – Identify frequent faculty needs and create quick-reference materials, while layering RD strategies into routine interactions.
3. **Leverage Institutional Resources** – Create partnerships across central and unit-level RA and RD staff to develop proposal libraries and strategic initiatives like program officer visits.
4. **Support Faculty at an Earlier Stage** – Establish processes to engage early-career faculty upon hiring, scaffold their learning, track their research goals, and offer staged and successive pre-award assistance.
5. **Pursue RD Professional Development** – Seek training through national organizations, connect RA duties to RD activities, and track skill development milestones.
6. **Refine Faculty Engagement Strategies** – Use focus groups and live polls over extensive surveys to gather feedback efficiently to improve outreach and support strategies.

RA staff members can engage early on with new faculty and layer support services to set the stage for an enhanced long-term working relationship.

For Research Development (RD) Staff and Professional RD Organizations

Research development professionals and organizations have valuable expertise and resources that can greatly benefit RA staff and institutional research capacity.

Strengthening collaboration between RD and RA professionals will create more seamless support for faculty, improve training offerings, and enhance overall grant success rates. By sharing knowledge, partnering on faculty development, and creating cross-institutional connections, RD professionals can help advance the research ecosystem alongside RA staff. The following recommendations focus on leveraging RD expertise to support RA staff and institutional research growth.

1. **Learn More about the RA Role** – By learning more about the roles and responsibilities of their RA colleagues, RD professionals will be better positioned to connect and share resources with them.
2. **Strengthen RD-RA Collaboration** – Create committees or structured pairings for knowledge sharing and joint faculty training initiatives.
3. **Share RD Resources with RA Staff** – Disseminate training materials, toolkits, and workshops to RA staff and invite them to RD conferences.
4. **Include RA Staff in RD Training** – Make RA colleagues a target learner group and provide one-on-one consultations for their grantsmanship development.
5. **Facilitate RD-RA Professional Organization Partnerships** – Develop cross-organizational initiatives, discounted joint memberships, and co-hosted events and co-convened conferences to blend these professional activities.
6. **Expand RD Knowledge for RA** – Publish articles, present workshops, and conduct training on RD topics relevant for and accessible by RA target audiences.

The RD field has valuable and desired resources that should be shared with RA colleagues, with partnerships formed for further growth and development.

For Senior Faculty, Administration, and Leadership

Strong institutional support is critical for enhancing research administration effectiveness and faculty success in grant-seeking. Leadership and senior faculty play a key role in fostering a culture of collaboration, providing resources, and ensuring RA staff are recognized as valuable research partners. By investing in staffing, process improvements, and professional development, institutions can create a more efficient and supportive research environment. The following recommendations outline key actions leadership can take to strengthen RA-faculty connections and improve institutional research competitiveness.

1. **Foster a Collaborative Culture** – Leadership should promote mutual respect between RA staff and faculty, supporting RA-led training and recognizing their contributions to institutional research achievements.
2. **Expand Research Support Staffing** – Increase staff where possible, utilize student workers for reiterative administrative tasks, and explore co-funding options with grant-active colleges.
3. **Enhance Proposal Submission Processes** – Reduce last-minute submissions by enforcing earlier deadlines for RA review and supporting strategies to increase faculty accountability and independence in the proposal development process, allowing for better pre-award support.
4. **Invest in Professional Development** – Provide RA staff with funding for multiple professional society memberships and conference attendances to broaden expertise.
5. **Align RA Roles with Institutional Goals** – Add RD-type support activities and goals into annual reviews and operational goals to formalize their recognition and impact for RA staff.

Leaders and senior faculty can help everyone in the institutional community appreciate and access RA staff expertise and impact.

For Early-Career Faculty

Early-career faculty benefit significantly from engaging with RA staff, who offer specialized knowledge and administrative expertise to support grant-seeking efforts. By building strong working relationships with RA professionals, both early-career and more experienced faculty can access critical resources, avoid common pitfalls, and enhance their competitiveness for external funding. Understanding basic research administration processes and leveraging institutional support early can lead to a more efficient and successful research career. The following recommendations provide guidance on how early-career faculty can maximize the benefits of RA support.

1. **Prepare to Engage RA Staff Support** – Utilize available training on budgets, proposals, and project management to enhance readiness, efficiency, and timeliness for working with RA staff.
2. **Leverage RA Staff Expertise** – Recognize their unique knowledge, tap their institutional knowledge, seek guidance early, and engage with them as strategic partners.
3. **Engage RA Staff throughout the Grant Process** – Plan for frequent collaboration with RA staff to enhance funding competitiveness and proposal success.
4. **Acknowledge RA Contributions to Grant Achievements** – For their help with submitting a grant proposal to assisting with a winning grant award, show appreciation for the contributions of RA support staff through thank-you emails to these staff members and praise about them to college, unit, and/or institutional leadership.

Early-career faculty have much to gain by engaging RA support staff, early and often, throughout their grant seeking journey.

CONCLUSION & NEXT STEPS

This project highlights the potential for integrating Research Development (RD) approaches into Research Administration (RA) roles to better support early-career faculty researchers. The findings confirm that many RA professionals are interested in expanding their roles, driven by a desire to make their work more meaningful and valuable, foster connection and collaboration, and enhance their own professional development. However, challenges such as workload constraints and institutional buy-in must be addressed. Next steps include further engagement with leadership to advocate for RA staff development, the creation of resources shared with RA communities to facilitate RD-oriented support, and continued exploration of best practices for integrating RD and RA functions across diverse institutional settings.

What We're Taking Away

Our work underscores the importance of collaboration between RA and RD professionals (and integration across their associated knowledgebases) in fostering a robust research support ecosystem. RA professionals already serve as key points of contact for faculty navigating grant processes. With additional RD-focused training and institutional backing, RA staff can play an even greater role in faculty success. Recognizing and investing in this integrated approach can lead to a more efficient and effective research infrastructure, particularly at institutions where dedicated RD staff may be limited and RA staff's RD interests are potentially remain untapped.

Where We (and Others) May Go Next

Future efforts should focus on strengthening partnerships between RA and RD organizations, facilitating professional development opportunities for RA staff, and advocating for institutional policies, communities, and cultures that support expanded RA-RD roles. Further research on the impact of RD-infused RA support on faculty grant success rates and institutional research growth will be valuable. Institutions and professional groups may look to pilot programs that formalize RD training within RA offices, creating scalable models for broader adoption in higher education research administration. Key to this work will be change at the leadership level in terms of how they view and reward the efforts of their RA staff members. Importantly, while R1 institutions may be initial test beds for these models, they should be adapted and further developed in non-R1 contexts to address unique institutional needs and opportunities.

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APPENDIX A: GLOSSARY OF KEY TERMS

Administrators and Leadership – Individuals in higher education institutions responsible for overseeing research and sponsored programs, academic programs, faculty development, and institutional policies. This includes department chairs, deans, provosts, and university presidents who influence research priorities and resource allocation.

Carnegie Foundation – An organization that classifies higher education institutions based on their research activity and educational mission.

Co-Principal Investigator (Co-PI) – A key member of a research project team who shares responsibility for the scientific and administrative oversight of a funded project but is not the lead investigator.

Early-Career Researchers – Assistant professors or other faculty in the early or emerging stages of their academic careers who are developing their research portfolios and seeking external funding.

Emerging Research Institution (ERI) – A college or university that is expanding its research capabilities and funding portfolio but has not yet achieved the classification of a top-tier research institution, which is typically indicated with the Carnegie Foundation “R1” classification. (*synonymous with “Research-Emerging Institution”*)

Exploratory Sequential Mixed Methods Design – A research methodology that begins with qualitative data collection and analysis (e.g., focus groups) to explore a topic, followed by quantitative data collection (e.g., surveys) to further test and refine findings.

Florida Research Administration Conference (FRAC) – A statewide professional conference that brings together research administrators and other institutional stakeholders to discuss best practices and emerging trends in research administration.

Florida Research Development Alliance (FL-RDA) – A statewide network of research developers and research administrators in Florida, dedicated to fostering collaboration and sharing best practices in research development support.

Minority-Serving Institution (MSI) – A designation for higher education institutions that enroll a significant percentage of students from minority backgrounds, including Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs), Hispanic-Serving Institutions (HSIs), Tribal Colleges and Universities (TCUs), and Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AANAPISIs).

National Council of University Research Administrators (NCURA) – A professional organization that provides education, collaboration, and resources for individuals involved in university research administration.

National Organization of Research Development Professionals (NORDP) – A professional association dedicated to the field of research development, offering resources and training to enhance institutional research competitiveness.

Non-R1 Institution – Universities and colleges that do not meet the Carnegie Classification criteria for the highest level of research activity. These institutions may still engage in research but typically have less research spending and doctoral programs than R1 institutions. (*synonymous with “Research-Emerging Institution” and “Emerging Research Institution”*)

Principal Investigator (PI) – The lead researcher responsible for the design, conduct, reporting, and management of a research project, particularly in the context of grant-funded research.

Primarily Undergraduate Institution (PUI) – Colleges and universities that focus primarily on undergraduate education, often with limited graduate programs and research funding.

R1 Institution – A classification for universities with the highest level of research activity, as designated by the Carnegie Classification of Institutions of Higher Education. These institutions receive significant external research funding and have extensive doctoral programming.

Research Administration (RA) – The field and profession encompassing the management of sponsored research and programs, including grant proposal submission, budget development, regulatory compliance, and fiscal oversight.

Research Development (RD) – A professional field and set of strategic activities aimed at enhancing an institution’s research capacity, including proposal development, faculty training, collaboration facilitation, and funding opportunity identification.

Research Ecosystem – The interconnected network of researchers, administrators, funding agencies, institutional policies, and support structures that collectively influence the research environment and productivity of an institution.

Research-Emerging Institution – A college or university that is expanding its research capabilities and funding portfolio but has not yet achieved the classification of a top-tier research institution, which is typically indicated with the Carnegie Foundation “R1” classification. (*synonymous with “Emerging Research Institution”*)

Research Infrastructure – The foundational resources, facilities, personnel, and administrative support necessary to conduct research at an institution. This includes laboratories, grant management systems, research computing, and compliance offices.

Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) – A broad academic and research discipline category encompassing fields that emphasize scientific and technical expertise.

Senior Faculty – Established faculty members, typically at the associate or full professor level, who have significant experience in research, teaching, and service who often mentor early-career faculty and contribute to institutional leadership and research development activities.

Sponsored Programs Office – A university office home to research administrators that is responsible for managing external research funding, ensuring compliance with regulations, and supporting faculty grant-seeking efforts.

APPENDIX B: PARTICIPANT DEMOGRAPHICS

This report emphasized data collected from RA staff members (NCURA and FRAC groups). Since information collected from all groups informed instrument development and interpretation of the data, demographic information from all participants in the larger project is included here.

Demographic data for focus group participants and survey respondents are presented. The focus groups that engaged statewide and national organizations (FL-RDA, NCURA, and FRAC) each included about 30 participants per event, organized into smaller discussion groups. Surveys were sent to the memberships of these organizations, with about 30 responses to two surveys and over 200 to the third survey (see **Figure 13**). One focus group involved the Advisory Committee on the project, composed of five individuals, with experience in both RA and RD professions.

Focus group and survey participants varied in the amount of RA versus RD work they engage in, years of job experience, and types of institutions they are currently affiliated with. Importantly, both major research universities and smaller colleges and universities were included in the sample, including minority-serving and primarily-undergraduate institutions. There was also a mix of public and private institutions.

	FL-RDA		NCURA		FRAC		Advisory Committee
	Focus Group	Survey	Focus Group	Survey	Focus Group	Survey	Focus Group
# participants	29	32	35	214	26	24	5
% RA	19%	22%	68%	59%	69%	75%	40%
% RD	56%	44%	8%	5%	12%	21%	60%
% RA/RD	26%	34%	4%	27%	0%	0%	--
Avg exp.	12 years	12 years	8 years	15 years	20 years	12 years	--
Range exp.	<1 to 25+ years	1 to 28 years	<1 to 35+ years	<1 to 45 years	3 to 27 years	<1 to 35 years	--
Institutions by Participant							
Public	20	21	12	135	20	23	4
Private	7	9	8	65	5	1	1
MSI	1	14	2	26	16	9	1
PUI	2	5	6	42	0	2	1
ERI	10	10	7	58	4	5	2

Figure 13: Demographics for RA and RD Professional Groups

Note: “FL-RDA” is the Florida Research Development Alliance, “NCURA” is the National Council of University Research Administrators, and “FRAC” is the Florida Research Administration Conference. “MSI” refers to Minority-Serving Institution, “PUI” to Primarily Undergraduate Institution, and “ERI” to Emerging Research Institution.

	Early-Career Faculty & Mentors	
	Focus Group	Survey
# participants	46	50
% assistant professors	64%	54%
% mentors	36%	46%
Avg. # grants submitted as PI/Co-PI	11 grants	19 grants
Range # grants submitted as PI/Co-PI	0 to 75 grants	0 to 200 grants
Sex and Race/Ethnicity		
% female	61%	56%
% male	39%	38%
% Asian	25%	8%
% Black	14%	6%
% Hispanic	14%	16%
% White (non-Hispanic)	39%	52%
% other race/ethnicity	11%	10%
Disciplines		
Engineering, technology, & computer science	16	9
Health & medical science	62	40
Humanities	3	2
Mathematics & physical science	5	3
Natural science	28	15
Social science	30	19
Institutions by Participant		
Public	10	11
Private	15	35
MSI	3	21
PUI	2	0
ERI	14	28

Figure 14: Demographics for Faculty and Mentor Groups

Another group from which information was collected through both focus group and survey methods included early-career faculty and those who mentor them at their institutions (see **Figure 14**). They were recruited through members of the FL-RDA organization. There were about 50 contributors to each, focus group and survey. More demographic and background information was collected from these groups, including their experiences with grant seeking, sex, race/ethnicity, disciplines, and institutional affiliation.

The range of experience in grant seeking was wide, spanning from no experience submitting grants as an investigator to 75 or more grants submitted in these roles.

There were more female participants than male, and most were White or Asian, though over 20% of each sample included Black and Hispanic faculty and administrators.

Most participants in this group were in the health and medical science disciplines, though a fair number were also in natural science; social science; and engineering, technology, and computer science.

Institutional affiliation included a combination of public and private institutions, minority-serving institutions, and emerging research institutions. Only a couple of primarily undergraduate institutions appeared in these samples.

Note: "FL-RDA" is the Florida Research Development Alliance. "PI" refers to Principal Investigator and "Co-PI" to Co-Principal Investigator. "MSI" refers to Minority-Serving Institution, "PUI" to Primarily Undergraduate Institution, and "ERI" to Emerging Research Institution.

APPENDIX C: RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES

Below is a listing of the 22 research development-oriented activities that were provided in relation to the survey results discussed starting on page 18 of this report. Survey questions asked RA staff to express interest in newly incorporating any of these RD activities into their work. Respondents were also asked about how they would incorporate a new RD activity into their work and what they would need in terms of support to do so. Respondents were also permitted to list “Other” RD-oriented activities of interest.

1. Find and disseminate funding opportunities
2. Promote individual funding opportunities or funders through events/workshops
3. Edit proposals and provide strategic feedback (e.g., logic, merit, fit)
4. Analyze proposal reviews and assist with resubmissions
5. Meet with faculty to strategize and make long-term plans to advance their research
6. Create faculty mentoring programs
7. Connect faculty with units/resources across campus (e.g., library, IT)
8. Facilitate faculty networking and collaboration
9. Organize visits from agency program officers
10. Host panels with successful grant awardees, senior researchers, etc.
11. Develop training materials, toolkits, or workshops for faculty
12. Facilitate team science and team building for researchers
13. Help enable collaborative/strategic partnerships
14. Communicate and promote faculty research (e.g., awards, accomplishments)
15. Manage online resources to support faculty researchers
16. Maintain a library of successful proposals
17. Coordinate multi-disciplinary interest groups of faculty
18. Connect researchers with diversity, education, and/or mentoring resources
19. Work with department chairs, college deans, or other leaders to customize support services
20. Analyze institutional and funder data to recommend funding opportunities
21. Advise institutional leadership on research-related topics
22. Increase institutional research capacity and strategic planning
23. Other (please specify): _____

